

PERCEIVED BARRIERS TO PHYSICAL ACTIVITY AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

The study is aimed at determining the effects of the school year, the academic record and the body mass index on the barriers to physical activity in a sample of 852 Spanish adolescents ($M = 14.9$; $DT = 1.75$). A descriptive and inferential analysis was carried out, after administration of the Self-Report Questionnaire of Barriers to Physical Activity Practice (SRQBPAP) adapted by Niñerola, Capdevila and Pintanel (2006). The results point as main barriers the obligations or lack of time, and fatigue or laziness. Likewise, adolescents perceive greater barriers to physical activity practice in upper-level courses, in which they exhibit better academic performance and a higher body mass index. In conclusion, addressing these barriers may help to minimize sedentary behavior in adolescents.

Key words

Physical activity, barriers, body mass index, school year, academic record.

Introduction

Despite the known health benefits of an active lifestyle, physical inactivity remains a problem among adolescents (Corder et al., 2015; Langguth, Könen, Matulis, Steil, Gawrilow & Stadler, 2015). In fact, students are aware that overweight is increasingly common, and the consequences it entails for long-term physical health (Wilkenfeld, Pagnini, Booth & King, 2008; Zabinski, Saelens, Stein, Hayden-Wade & Wilfley, 2003).

Therefore, the increase in sedentary lifestyle of the entire population, especially in adolescence, and among girls, with potentially serious long-term consequences for physical and mental health, has become an issue of growing importance in recent decades (Dwyer, Allison, Goldenberg, Fein, Yoshida & Boutilier, 2006; Langguth et al., 2015). Girls are generally less physically active than boys, but little is known about the reasons or how they are different from the girls who are more physically active (AlQuaiz & Tayel, 2009; Rajaraman, Correa, Punthakee, Lear, Jayachitra & Swaminathan, 2015; Youssef, Al Shafie, Al-Mukhaini, & Al-Balushi, 2013). However, we do know that they tend to be higher, with lower body mass and fat indexes, they score higher in self-efficacy, motivation toward physical activity, self-management strategies, or the support of family and friends (Ross, Dowda, Beets, & Pate, 2013). Consequently, the analysis of these barriers which hinder or prevent the practice of physical activity, is important not only for avoiding them, but also because the perception of these barriers is associated with a greater prevalence of leisure-time physical inactivity among adolescents (Dias, Loch, & Ronque, 2015).

Among the barriers to physical activity, there are several factors. First, the lack of time (Awadalla et al., 2014; Kimberly, Hultquist, & McLester, 2013; Musaiger et al., 2013; Rodríguez-Romo, Boned-Pascual, & Garrido-Muñoz, 2009), or the fact that the structured activities which favor physical activity are focused during the school stage and the subject of Physical Education (Kumar, Adhikari, Li, Lindshield, Muturi, & Kidd, 2016).

On the other hand, the lack of motivation toward the practice of physical activity and the pressure of the educational tasks detract from the physical activity priority in the everyday life (Peykari et al., 2015; Youssef et al., 2013). To this must be added the lack of a safe environment for practicing physical activity, especially for girls, and the high cost of certain professional sports (Rajaraman et al., 2015). The study conducted by Nicholson et al. (2013) has added to these barriers the lack of motivation, environmental factors (e.g. transportation) and health problems. Mailey, Huberty, Dinkel and McAuley (2014) have included family responsibilities, guilt, lack of support, and scheduling and work constraints.

Other constraints include the fact that the scheduled activities take place at the end of the school day, the duration of the sessions, and the short duration of the program (Vergara, Santibañez, Herrera, & Argote, 2012), low spirits, lack of will or energy, interest in other activities (Quaiz, & Tayel, 2009; Youssef et al., 2013), little support

from teachers (Musaiger et al., 2013; Owen, Astell-Burt, & Lonsdale, 2013), or little social support, lack of resources, working requirements and family (Rodriguez-Romo, Boned-Pascual, & Garrido-Muñoz, 2009), limited opportunities to participate in the physical activity, or lack of programs (Perry, & Hoffman, 2010; Wilkenfeld, Pagnini, Booth, & King, 2008), and overuse of visual display terminals (VDTs) (Langguth et al., 2015).

In a longitudinal qualitative study on obese youngsters aged 14 to 18 years, Peeters et al. (2012) have pointed out among the barriers perceived by these adolescents the ability to access a gym, the need for initial trainer supervision, a wide range of activities, the provision of collective games, as well as the importance of family and partner's support (Musaiger et al., 2014), the environmental context or built environment (Ding, & Gebel, 2012).

Therefore, the barriers and the extent of their association with physical inactivity depend on the population studied (Ibrahim, Karim, Lai Oon, & Wan Ngah, 2013). Consequently, the objectives of this study are to find out the main reasons that hinder the practice of physical activity and to determine the influence of the school year, academic record and body mass index on the barriers to the practice of physical activity in adolescent populations.

Method

Participants

The study included 852 students enrolled in Compulsory Secondary Education (CSE) and Upper Secondary Education (USE) of public schools from the Autonomous Community of Galicia (Spain), using a non-probabilistic and intentional sampling method. Thus, 144 students are enrolled in the 1st year of CSE, 130 in the 2nd year, 144 in the 3rd year, 184 in 4th year, 154 in the 1st year of USE, and 96 in the 2nd year. In addition, 17.1% of students have always passed all the subjects, 46.8% have failed certain subjects, and 36% were retained at least once throughout their academic history. Finally, the Body Mass Index (BMI) was categorized as low weight (<20, 42.1% of students), normal weight (20 to 25, 48.4% of students), and overweight (> 25, 9.5% of students). Their age ranged from 12 to 17 years ($M=14.9$; $SD=1.75$).

Instrument

First, an ad hoc questionnaire was developed, which included the sociodemographic variables (school year, academic record and BMI) and, second, the Self-Report Questionnaire of Barriers to Physical Activity Practice (SRQBPAP; Capdevila, 2005), adapted by Niñerola, Capdevila and Pintanel (2006), was employed. This version consists of 17 items that are answered on a Likert scale ranging from 0 (reason unlikely to prevent me from performing physical activity in the next few weeks) to 10 (reason most likely to prevent me from performing physical activity)

points. The original study reported four different subscales (body image/physical-social anxiety, fatigue/laziness, obligations/lack of time, environment/facilities) with good reliability and adequate validity.

Procedure

The questionnaire was collectively administered to Compulsory Secondary Education students during regular school hours, during the academic year 2016-2017. After communicating the appropriate instructions and once the informed consent form was signed (by school and families), all students voluntarily completed the requested information. The ethical research protocols were fulfilled with special emphasis on confidentiality. The study was conducted according to the ethical standards established by the Declaration of Helsinki (1975).

Data analysis

The means, standard deviations and response rates were calculated for each item of the questionnaire. In addition, to obtain the results on the main effects of the interaction between the different variables, analyses of variance (one-factor ANOVA) and a post hoc analysis were performed using Scheffé's method. The effect size (Cohen's *d*) was also calculated. All analyses were performed with the SPSS 21.0 statistical package (IBM Corp., 2012).

Results

Level of barriers hindering the practice of physical activity perceived by adolescents

Taking into account the results obtained (Table 1), it is observed that obligations or lack of time, and fatigue or laziness are considered the main barriers that hinder the practice of physical activity. In particular, students mention impediments such as being very busy, not having time, having family obligations, lack of will and being tired or fatigued. On the contrary, the less important barriers are body image or physical-social anxiety, and environment or facilities. In this case, the most recurrent reasons are feeling embarrassed, not feeling comfortable, inadequate facilities and living too far from the place where physical activity is performed.

Table 1.

Descriptors of SRQBPAP items based on frequency

Order	Item	Factor	Statement	<i>M</i>	<i>S.D.</i>	<i>Low</i> ◀ <i>Probability (%)</i> ▶ <i>High</i>				
						1	2	3	4	5
1st	4	O/LoT	Having too much work to do	2.60	1.43	33.9	14.3	24	13.2	14.6
2nd	2	F/L	Being lazy	2.23	1.39	44.2	21.1	14.6	8.2	12
3rd	11	O/LoT	Not finding the time for physical activity	2.22	1.39	46.5	16.1	15.8	11.7	9.9
4th	9	F/L	Lack of consistency	1.89	1.25	57.6	14.9	14.6	6.1	6.7
5th	5	F/L	Having muscle fever or muscle	1.69	1.06	63.2	16.4	12	5.6	2.9

			pain as a result of physical activity								
6th	7	O/LoT	Having too many family obligations	1.67	1.04	63.2	16.7	12.6	5	2.6	
7th	12	F/L	Feeling tiredness or fatigue usually throughout the day	1.65	1.11	67.3	14	9.6	4.4	4.7	
8th	10	BI/PSA	Thinking that other people are in better shape than I am	1.63	1.17	72.2	9.1	7.9	5.3	5.6	
9th	6	BI/PSA	Feeling that my physical appearance is worse than that of others	1.52	1.01	73.4	11.4	7.6	4.7	2.9	
10th	13	BI/PSA	Thinking that others judge me for my physical appearance	1.51	1.05	75.1	10.5	5.6	5	3.8	
11th	8	F/L	Not being "fit" to perform physical activity	1.51	.99	74	9.6	9.9	3.8	2.6	
12th	1	F/L	Tiring myself out during physical activity or fear of getting injured	1.50	.89	69.3	17.5	8.5	2.9	1.8	
13th	14	E/F	Living too far from the place where I can perform physical activity	1.48	.88	71.3	15.2	8.5	3.8	1.2	
14th	16	BI/PSA	Feeling ashamed because they are watching me while I perform physical activity	1.45	1.01	78.9	8.5	5.3	3.2	4.1	
15th	15	BI/PSA	Not feeling comfortable with people who perform physical activity with me	1.34	.80	79.5	11.7	5.3	1.8	1.8	
16th	17	E/F	The fact that the facilities or the instructors are not suitable	1.33	.81	80.1	12.3	3.8	1.8	2	
17th	3	BI/PSA	Feeling uncomfortable about my appearance while dressed in sportswear	1.31	.83	83.9	7.3	4.1	2.6	2	

BI/PSA = *Body image/Physical-social anxiety*; F/L = *Fatigue/Laziness*; O/LoT = *Obligations/Lack of time*; E/F = *Environment/Facilities*

Differences in the perceived level of barriers to the practice of physical activity by school year

Regarding the school year variable (Table 2), there are significant differences in the barriers: fatigue/laziness ($F_{(5, 846)} = 4.23$; $p < .001$), Scheffé's method confirming that they occur between those who are enrolled in the 3rd year of CSE and those in the 1st year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .43$), those who are enrolled in the 4th year of CSE and those in the 1st year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .46$), those who are enrolled in the 1st year of USE and those in the 1st year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .45$), and those enrolled in the 2nd year of USE and those in the 1st year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .43$); and in terms of obligations/lack of time ($F_{(5, 846)} = 11.74$; $p < .001$), Scheffé's method pointing out that they occur between those who are enrolled in the 4th year of CSE and those in the 1st year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .40$), those enrolled in the 1st year of USE and those in the 1st year of CSE (large effect size $d = .69$), those enrolled in the 2nd year of USE and those in the 1st year of CSE (large effect size $d = .75$), those enrolled in the 1st year of USE and those in the 2nd year of

CSE (mean effect size $d = .56$), those enrolled in the 2nd year of USE and those in the 2nd year of CSE (large effect size $d = .62$), those enrolled in the 1st year of USE and those in the 3rd year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .43$), those enrolled in the 2nd year of USE and those in the 3rd year of CSE (mean effect size $d = .48$), and between those enrolled in the 1st year of USE and those in the 4th year of CSE (small effect size $d = .31$). There are no significant differences according to the school year in the following factors: body image/physical-social anxiety ($F_{(5, 846)} = 2.56$; $p > .05$) and environment/facilities ($F_{(5, 846)} = 1.77$; $p > .05$).

Table 2.
ANOVA based on school year frequency

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY BARRIERS		M	SD	F/p	Scheffé's method	Cohen's d
Body image/ Physical- Social anxiety	1st year of CSE	11.76	9.30	2.56 $p > .05$	---	---
	2nd year of CSE	11.99	10.44			
	3rd year of CSE	12.13	9.38			
	4th year of CSE	12.14	10.66			
	1st year of USE	11.32	8.35			
	2nd year of USE	10.40	8.50			
Fatigue/ Laziness	1st year of CSE	12.93	8.28	4.23 $p < .001$	3rd CSE - 1st CSE 4th CSE - 1st CSE 1st USE - 1st CSE 2nd USE - 1st CSE	.43 .46 .45 .43
	2nd year of CSE	15.78	10.02			
	3rd year of CSE	16.79	9.49			
	4th year of CSE	17.18	9.94			
	1st year of USE	16.86	9.22			
	2nd year of USE	16.70	9.08			
Obligations/ Lack of time	1st year of CSE	9.13	5.63	11.74 $p < .001$	4th CSE - 1st CSE 1st USE - 1st CSE 2nd USE - 1st CSE 1st USE - 2nd CSE 2nd USE - 2nd CSE 1st USE - 3rd CSE 2nd USE - 3rd CSE 1st USE - 4th CSE	.40 .69 .75 .56 .62 .43 .48 .31
	2nd year of CSE	9.76	6.34			
	3rd year of CSE	10.62	6.51			
	4th year of CSE	11.48	6.24			
	1st year of USE	13.53	7.06			
	2nd year of USE	13.78	6.67			
Environment/ Facilities	1st year of CSE	3.31	2.28	1.77 $p > .05$	---	---
	2nd year of CSE	3.83	3.27			
	3rd year of CSE	3.86	2.68			
	4th year of CSE	3.73	2.82			
	1st year of USE	3.72	2.63			
	2nd year of USE	3.71	2.31			

Differences in the perceived level of barriers to the practice of physical activity based on the academic record

Statistically significant differences were found based on the academic record in all the barriers analyzed (Table 3): body image/physical-social anxiety ($F_{(2, 849)} = 6.78$; $p < .05$), Scheffé's method confirming that they occur between those who always pass

and the retained students (mean effect size $d = .35$); fatigue/laziness ($F_{(2, 849)} = 12.89$; $p < .001$), Scheffé's method stating that they occur between those who always pass and those who fail certain subjects (mean effect size $d = .39$), and between those who always pass and the retained students (mean effect size $d = .49$); obligations/lack of time ($F_{(2, 849)} = 7.36$; $p < .05$), Scheffé's method showing that they occur between those who fail certain subjects and those who pass (small effect size $d = .26$), and between the retained students and those who pass (mean effect size $d = .40$); and environment/facilities ($F_{(2, 849)} = 3.28$; $p < .05$), Scheffé's method proving that they occur between those who always pass and those who were retained at least once (small effect size $d = .25$).

Table 3.

ANOVA based on students' academic record

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY BARRIERS		M	SD	F/p	Scheffé's method	Cohen's d
Body image/ Physical-Social anxiety	Pass	13.83	11.39	6.78 $p < .05$	Pass-Ret.	.35
	Fail	11.95	9.77			
	Ret.	10.38	8.01			
Fatigue/Laziness	Pass	19.54	10.22	12.89 $p < .001$	Pass-Fail Pass-Ret.	.39 .49
	Fail	15.73	9.44			
	Ret.	14.86	8.77			
Obligations/Lack of time	Pass	9.63	5.67	7.36 $p < .05$	Fail-Pass Ret.-Pass	.26 .40
	Fail	11.26	6.60			
	Ret.	12.15	6.89			
Environment/Facilities	Pass	4.09	2.97	3.28 $p < .05$	Pass-Ret.	.25
	Fail	3.75	2.76			
	Ret.	3.42	2.46			

Differences in the perceived level of barriers to the practice of physical activity based on BMI

In terms of body mass index (BMI), there are statistically significant differences in all the barriers analyzed (Table 4): body image/physical-social anxiety ($F_{(2, 849)} = 20.51$; $p < .001$), Scheffé's method confirming that they occur between those with normal weight and those with low weight (mean effect size $d = .32$), those with overweight and those with low weight (large effect size $d = .67$), and those with overweight and those with normal weight (mean effect size $d = .35$); fatigue/laziness ($F_{(2, 849)} = 6.63$; $p < .05$), Scheffé's method showing that they occur between those with overweight and those with low weight (mean effect size $d = .42$), and between those with overweight and those with normal weight (mean effect size $d = .31$); obligations/lack of time ($F_{(2, 849)} = 4.66$; $p < .05$), Scheffé's method pointing out that they occur between those with overweight and those with low weight (mean effect size $d = .36$), and between those with overweight and those with normal weight (mean effect size $d = .33$); and

environment/facilities ($F_{(2, 849)} = 7.25; p < .05$), Scheffé's method proving they occur between those with overweight and those with low weight (mean effect size $d = .41$), and between those with overweight and those with normal weight (mean effect size $d = .33$).

Table 4.

ANOVA based on the frequency of body mass index (BMI)

PHYSICAL ACTIVITY BARRIERS		M	SD	F/L	Scheffé's method	Cohen's d
Body image/ Physical- Social anxiety	Low weight	9.72	6.62	20.51 $p < .001$	Normal weight-low weight	.32
	Normal weight	12.48	10.44		Overweight-Low weight	.67
	Overweight	16.58	12.99		Overweight-Normal weight	.35
Fatigue/ Laziness	Low weight	15.22	8.67	6.63 $p < .05$	Overweight-Low weight	.42
	Normal weight	16.16	9.67		Overweight-Normal weight	.31
	Overweight	19.43	11.12			
Obligations/ Lack of time	Low weight	10.96	6.51	4.66 $p < .05$	Overweight-Low weight	.36
	Normal weight	11.19	6.54		Overweight-Normal weight	.33
	Overweight	13.40	7.04			
Environment/ Facilities	Low weight	3.48	2.36	7.25 $p < .05$	Overweight-Low weight	.41
	Normal weight	3.67	2.72		Overweight-Normal weight	.33
	Overweight	4.74	3.62			

Discussion

This work was performed to determine the main barriers that have an impact on the abandonment of physical activity and to analyze which sociodemographic variables (school year, academic record and body mass index) should be particularly stressed, with the aim of leading to a more active adolescence. Thus, the objective of the study was to examine the barriers which hinder physical activity and to determine the effect of the school year, academic record and BMI on the factors that make up these barriers.

Concerning the barriers that hinder the practice of physical activity, adolescents provide greater importance to obligations or lack of time and fatigue or laziness, as shown by the works conducted by Kimm et al. (2006), Springer, Kelder, and Hoelscher (2006), Del Hoyo, and Sañudo (2007), Serra-Puyal, Generelo-Lanaspa, and Zaragoza-Casterad (2010), Kimberly, Hultquist, and McLester, (2013), Awadalla et al., (2014). Less important barriers are those referring to their body image/physical-social anxiety and environment/facilities.

Therefore, the interventions to increase adolescent physical activity should begin before adolescence. Authors such as Huang, Gillman, Field, Austin, Colditz, and

Frazier (2008) proved that these activities were more effective if they were multimodal and focused on a specific target group, as well as family and environmental factors.

According to the results, when the physical activity barriers were associated with the school year, the fatigue/laziness factor was found to be significant, upper-level students (3rd and 4th of CSE, and 1st and 2nd of USE) presenting greater impediments when it comes to performing physical activity. Likewise, the obligations/lack of time factor was also found to be significant, corresponding to the upper-level students (4th year of CSE, 1st and 2nd year of USE) as greater barriers to the practice of physical activity. Consequently, adolescents enrolled in upper-level courses presented higher values in the barriers to physical activity. This conclusion is directly related to the studies stating that regular practice of physical activity is abandoned in adolescence (Corder et al., 2015).

Regarding the academic record, the results showed that adolescents who pass all subjects present higher values in the barriers related to body image/ physical-social anxiety, fatigue/laziness, and environment/facilities. On the contrary, in the obligations/lack of time factor, students who failed certain subjects or retained students reached higher values. These results are partly different from those obtained in other studies, which demonstrate a positive relationship between academic performance and physical activity (Cacciotti, Milne, & Orr, 2015; Howie, & Pate, 2012; Rasberry et al., 2011). Therefore, there is evidence suggesting that increased physical activity improves academic performance in children, however it is not known how they are interrelated (Kantomaa et al., 2013; Keeley, & Fox, 2009).

Finally, in terms of body mass index, the results showed that overweight adolescents presented higher levels in all barriers. These data are in agreement with the research studies claiming that physical inactivity may have negative consequences for young people (Bailey, Hillman, Arentn, & Petitpas, 2013; Fernández, Canet, & Giné-Garriga, 2017; Hills, Andersen, & Byrne, 2011; Rauner, Mess, & Woll 2013;).

Hence, planning for health promotion interventions should take into account not only adolescents' knowledge on the importance of physical activity, but also the barriers that prevent or hinder the practice of physical activity. The scientific evidence points to upper-level courses, good academic records and overweight as essential intervention factors in physical activity to counteract sedentary behavior among adolescents. However, this study presents certain limitations, such as the random selection of the sample, being narrowed down to a certain age range or region, or the effect of bias on the results due to falsification or social desirability in the self-report measures.

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